

OCEAN:ICE News – May 2024

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to the May's OCEAN:ICE News! We're thrilled to keep you updated on the latest from the world of OCEAN:ICE.

This month feels like the OCEAN:ICE is in its full swing. We have just welcomed a new partner to the project, submitted multiple project deliverables and milestones, and hosted three storyline meetings. At this very moment, we are co-organising the Southern Ocean Summer School with SO-CHIC, which is taking place in Cargèse, France. We are now also preparing for OCEAN:ICE's participation in the IMDIS 2024 conference, as well as planning engaging Climate Coffees.

Enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to bringing you more news in June!

Partner in the Spotlight: The National Antarctic Scientific Center of Ukraine (NASC)

NASC is the Ukrainian National Antarctic Scientific Center. The Center is the main organisation in Ukraine for conducting research in Antarctica as well as the Southern Ocean. It operates the fully equipped year-round Vernadsky research base (former British 'Faraday' base), easily reachable on Galindez Island (maritime Antarctic, near Antarctic peninsula). The three types of research - meteorological, biological and geophysical - are conducted there.

Besides, the NASC owns the unique research vessel of ice class 'Noosfera' (former RRS 'James Clark Ross'), which will also be used for OCEAN:ICE purposes.

Ukraine has the status of a Consultative Party to the Antarctic Treaty.

To date, the Center has organised and provided [28 Ukrainian Antarctic expeditions](#) and continuous work and ongoing research at Vernadsky research base.

Learn more about NASC [here](#) and NASC's [contribution](#) to OCEAN:ICE.

OCEAN:ICE

**STATE INSTITUTION
NATIONAL ANTARCTIC
SCIENTIFIC CENTER**
Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine

Национальний антарктичний науковий центр
National Antarctic Scientific Center of Ukraine

 OCEAN:ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN:ICE Activities

OCEAN:ICE Deliverables and Milestones Submitted

The OCEAN:ICE community has been very busy recently submitting multiple deliverables and milestones:

- D1.1 ‘Standardisation of Pan-Antarctic Mooring and Profiles’
- D3.2 ‘Report on Freshwater Fluxes from Surface Mass Budget and Sub-Shelf Melt in Antarctica’
- D5.5 ‘Temporal and Spatial Length Scales in $\delta^{18}O$ Observations’
- MS15 ‘OCEAN:ICE Data Infrastructure 1’
- MS24 ‘OCEAN:ICE WP8 Annual Storyline Meeting 2’

The progress and results of OCEAN:ICE are published in deliverables and milestone reports.

In order to keep up with the OCEAN:ICE deliverables and milestones, visit our [website](#) and stay tuned on our social media channels.

OCEAN:ICE Storyline Meetings

In OCEAN:ICE, we run storyline meetings which we use as a communication tool so that the work packages in the project can talk together across the following cross-cutting themes:

- Deep uncertainty in freshwater fluxes
- Bottom water and lower cell
- Oxygen isotope exploitation
- The role of pole(s) in the global climate system

The cross-cutting theme ‘The role of pole(s) in the global climate system’ met on the 29th of April 2024. The [University of Reading's Robin Smith](#) led the meeting.

‘Deep uncertainty in freshwater fluxes’ met on the 2nd of May 2024. The meeting was led by [Université libre de Bruxelles' Frank Pattyn](#).

‘Bottom water and lower cell’ met on the 3rd of May 2024. [British Antarctic Survey's Povl Abrahamsen](#) led the meeting.

This series of storyline meetings contribute to OCEAN:ICE's [milestones](#).

The Southern Ocean Summer School (SOSS) 2024

The Southern Ocean Summer School (SOSS) 2024 for Early-Career Scientists has started this week on the 7th of May 2024 and it will last until the 18th of May 2024. SOSS 2024 is hosted in Corsica, in the small village of Cargèse, at the [Institut d'Etudes Scientifiques de Cargèse](#) (IESC).

SOSS 2024 provides a unique opportunity for research master students, graduate students, and first-year postdocs to dive into the fascinating world of Southern Ocean sciences. The intensive program is designed to expand knowledge and deepen understanding of this crucial region of the world.

Read more about the Southern Ocean Summer School (SOSS) 2024 on our [website](#).

OCEAN:ICE and SO-CHIC present...

The Southern Ocean Summer School

7 - 18 May 2024 | Cargèse, France

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 SO-CHIC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement Nr. 821001.

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

OCEAN:ICE Knowledge Hub

Head over to the OCEAN:ICE [Knowledge Hub](#) where you can find resources to learn about the project and share with others. Here you can find articles where OCEAN:ICE has been in the [news](#), [OCEAN:ICE Breakers](#), [Factsheets and Infographics](#), [Webinars](#), [Workshops and Sessions](#).

Upcoming Events

OCEAN:ICE at IMDIS

OCEAN:ICE project partner [ETI](#) will present a poster entitled "Information systems and tools to support Antarctic communities" at the International Conference on Marine Data and Information Systems (IMDIS) 2024. This will show how collaborative efforts of stakeholders (such as the OCEAN:ICE and its link with SOOS) represent a significant step towards a more comprehensive understanding of Antarctic Ocean dynamics and their profound implications for global climate and ocean processes.

Learn more about OCEAN:ICE presence at IMDIS 2024 on our [website](#).

 OCEAN:ICE

OCEAN:ICE at IMDIS

27 - 29 May 2024 | Bergen & Online

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Happening Soon

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 7-18 May 2024, [Southern Ocean Summer School](#), Cargese
- 27-29 May 2024, [IMDIS](#), Bergen & online
- 12-13 June 2024, [Digital Ocean Forum](#), Brussels
- 19-21 June 2024, [FRISP 2024](#), Bremerhaven

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

Are you following us on Social Media?

Stay up to date with OCEAN:ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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